

**ANALYZING THE PROBLEMS FACED BY MONOLINGUALS
AND BILINGUALS DEVELOPING “GENITIVE CASE”
IN ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE**

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Abstract:

The objective of the present study was to find out whether the monolinguals and bilinguals learning English as a foreign language in Iran commit similar or different errors in learning the different types of the genitive case. A total number of 120 male and female English learners at three levels of English proficiency took part in the study. Out of these participants, 60 were monolinguals whose native language was Persian and 60 were bilinguals who spoke Turkish as the first language and Persian as the second one. They were selected randomly from different Iranian EFL learning institutes. To collect the learners' errors, a genitive test based on possible errors due to interference from Turkish and Persian language was designed and administered. To ensure the reliability of the test, the internal consistency of 'Chronbach's Alpha' was employed. The errors of the two groups (Monolinguals & Bilinguals) were identified and classified according to the different types of genitive case. Then, the sources of the errors were established by the principles of 'error analysis'. The results indicated that both groups committed similar errors, though to a varying degree. The sources of errors seem to be attributed to transfer from both Turkish and Persian language. Another finding is that, the similarities between languages, either between Persian and English or between Turkish and English did not prevent their speakers from committing errors; in conclusion, the idea of positive transfer due to similarities between native and target

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language needs to be treated cautiously. This study confirms the effect of the negative transfer from both the mother tongue and the second language on the target language.

Keywords: genitive case, bilinguals, monolinguals

1. Introduction

A research-based knowledge of characteristics of errors committed by language learners helps teachers, material developers and test designers to design lesson plans, prepare learning activities, and evaluate learners' achievement based on scientific information rather than speculation. A glance at the population of English learners in Iran indicates that a great number of them come from bilingual communities, developing Turkish, Gilaki, Kurdish, Lurish, etc. as their mother tongue, and then Persian as their second language. Thus, it seems necessary to know, firstly, what overgeneralizations of the native language rules monolinguals commit while learning English as a FL, and secondly, whether bilinguals make overgeneralizations of the rules in their mother tongues or the second language for that matter.

1.1. Research Questions

Two questions were to be answered in the study:

1. Do monolinguals and bilinguals commit the same errors?
2. What are the sources of their errors?

1.2. Research Hypotheses

1. Monolinguals and bilinguals commit different errors while learning English as a foreign language.
2. The errors monolinguals and bilinguals commit while learning English as a foreign language are due to a variety of sources.

2. Literature review

Based on James' (1980, p.3), definition of contrastive analysis, "*Contrastive analysis (CA) is a linguistic enterprise aimed at producing inverted (i.e. contrastive, not comparative) two-valued typologies (a CA is always concerned with a pair of languages), and founded on the assumption that languages can be compared*". Therefore, contrastive analysis claimed that LI interference is the main cause of learners' errors; and examining the corresponding

features of the L1 and L2 would lead to a viable syllabus of learning a second language by predicting the problematic area.

According to Ziahosseiny (2006, p. 13), *"the principle of stimulus generalization, says human beings learn on the basis of similarities and make errors on the basis of similarities"*. In addition, Corder (1981) believed that, errors are tools used by language learners in order to learn, and these errors are the necessary part of the language learning process. Selinker (1992, p. 119) also stated *"a modern belief would consider errors as part of the circular progression in learning, viewing them as a dynamic process involved in the learning process."* Moreover, according to Brown (2007), the occurrence of errors in L2 learners' production is unavoidable. He (2007, pp. 263- 266) classified sources of errors into four categories:

1. Interlingual transfer; that is the beginning stages of learning a second language are especially vulnerable to interlingual transfer from the native language, or interference.
2. Intralingual transfer; that is within the target language itself and is a major factor in second language learning.
3. Context of learning; that is a third major source of error, although it overlaps both types of transfer is the context of learning. 'Context' refers, for example, to the classroom with its teacher and its material in the case of school learning or the social situation in the case of untutored second language learning.
4. Communication strategies: learners obviously use production strategies in order to enhance getting their messages across, but at times these techniques can themselves become a source of error.

Olusoji (2013) identified morphological and syntactic errors in the essays of the Yoruba (a Nigerian language)/ English bilingual students. These errors were the result of the existing differences between two languages. The main objective of the study was to identify the effects of bilingualism on the morphology and syntax on the students' essays, determine whether the identified effects have any negative consequences on the students' overall linguistic performance and offer useful suggestions that will help to minimize the identified negative effects on the learners' language performance. Because Yoruba and English are two completely different languages, learners encountered problems in learning English language.

Another investigation was conducted by Sokeng in 2014 in Cameroon. He identified the difficulties that bilingual level 1 Francophone students faced in English and different types of the grammatical errors in their written texts. The analyses of their compositions revealed that the participants had difficulty in English grammar. The findings showed the most salient grammatical errors in the students' essays.

Several studies have been administered in the field of "Genitive case". One of them is a research that has been carried out by Mugurio (2013). She analyzed the use of attributive possessive structures, especially the pre-nominal possessive ('s possessive or genitive case) and post-nominal prepositional constructions (of possessive) by Argentinian learners of English. She described and analyzed possessive structures 's and *of*, and their contrasts in English and Spanish. Her study focused on 'attributive possession'. She said that students make mistakes during their learning process, and the way in which errors are treated, or ignored, is very important for the development of teaching attitudes towards error and correction. One of the students' errors was the combinations like '*life story*' and '*bank manager*' in which the first noun usually carries an adjectival value and can cause problems for students who might think about them as attributes.

Hedeshi (2012) compared and contrasted verb tenses in English and Persian languages with each other in order to find out Persian monolingual speakers' difficulties while learning English as a foreign language. She analyzed all verb tenses except continuous past perfect, past recognizance continuous and future continuous, because of their lack of use. She found out the learners have difficulty learning and using simple past, past continuous, future perfect, future perfect continuous and some cases in simple present and present perfect tenses. The results of her study showed that Persian speakers will face some difficulties in learning some certain tenses in English language which have little differences with their counterparts in their native language.

Keshavarz (2004) conducted a research on Turkish-Persian bilinguals, Armenian-Persian bilinguals, and Persian monolinguals in order to investigate their performance on a controlled productive ability vocabulary test. The results of her study showed that native speakers of Turkish and Armenian who speak Persian as their second language performed better in English vocabulary test than the Persian monolingual learners of English.

3. Methodology

3.1. Participants

The participants of the study included 120 male and female English learners. Out of these participants, 60 were monolinguals and 60 were bilinguals. Monolingual participants spoke Persian, while bilinguals spoke Turkish as their mother tongue, and Persian as their second language. The research was conducted in Iran where Persian is the official language of the country. However, in Turkish regions from which bilingual participants were selected, native people first learn Turkish as their first language and

then Persian as the second language. The participants were selected from both Turkish regions and Persian ones. The sampling procedure was a combination of both purposive and random sampling. The participants were at elementary, pre-intermediate, and intermediate levels of English proficiency. The purpose behind this choice was that the probability of finding errors by participants was supposed to be higher in these levels of English proficiency. Therefore, the number of participants studying English at elementary, pre-intermediate and intermediate levels, in each group of monolinguals and bilinguals, were 35, 15, and 10, respectively. These numbers were chosen deliberately to increase the probability of finding more errors. But the participants in each group of English proficiency were chosen randomly. They were 16 to 30 years old and their level of English proficiency had been determined through final exams of the institutes and placement tests of the institutes.

3.2. Instruments

To elicit errors related to genitive cases in English and to determine the source of errors, a genitive test was designed. To design the test, first, a thorough literature study was conducted to identify the genitive cases in English and their equivalents in both Turkish and Persian. Through analysis and comparison, the possible errors due to the interference from Turkish language and Persian one were also identified. After designing ample instances of possible errors due to the negative effect of Turkish and Persian languages, writing of test items started. The developed test was of multiple-choice type and totally contained 35 items with each item including three alternative answers. One of the alternatives was the correct answer and the other two alternatives were wrong answers. One of the wrong answers was due to the negative effect of the Persian language and the other one, due to the negative effect of the Turkish language. The Persian translation of the items was also included to avoid wrong comprehension of items. To ensure the reliability of the genitive test, the internal consistency of Cronbach's Alpha was employed. The value for Chronbach's Alpha proved to be 0.73 which is an acceptable index of internal consistency (Pallant, 2013). To find the answers to research questions, frequency counts were conducted.

3.3. Data Collection and Procedure

The genitive test in the form of paper and pencil test was administered. Students were told that the test was for research purpose and they didn't need to write their names. Those students who were interested to know their scores on the test were asked to write their names on the test paper. Totally, students had 45 minutes to answer the questions. After collecting the tests, calculation began by counting the number of errors in each

genitive type. All errors were identified and put in appropriate category. All errors were classified into three categories of wrong answers by Persian speakers, wrong answers by bilinguals due to the effect of Turkish language and wrong answers by bilinguals due to the effect of Persian language (second language). Wrong answers by monolinguals (Persian speakers) that fell into category of wrong answers due to the effect of Turkish language were not entered into the analysis. All errors were tabulated and classified based on the source of errors.

4. Results

As seen in the table 4.1, the most frequent errors have been found in *possessive s* category both by monolinguals and bilinguals. Therefore, it is concluded that possessive *s* has been the most difficult category for both bilinguals and monolinguals. In this sense, language does not have anything to do with it. However, it should not be forgotten that totally bilinguals committed more errors. In other words, they committed 154 errors affected by Persian language and 152 errors affected by Turkish language in *possessive s* errors category.

The next frequent category was possessive pronouns for monolinguals in terms of number of errors while it was possessive adjective category for bilinguals. Interestingly possessive adjective category which was the most frequent category in terms of number of errors after possessive pronoun for monolinguals, it was the possessive pronouns for bilinguals after possessive adjectives.

Among the genitives by *for*, *of*, and *from*, genitive by *for* was the most frequent one in terms of number of errors for both monolinguals and bilinguals. It can be concluded that this category has been the most problematic for both monolinguals and bilinguals. The least frequent category in terms of number of errors was genitives by *of* for the monolinguals while it was genitives by *from* for the bilinguals.

With respect to errors due to the language effect, the number of errors due to the effect of Turkish language was greater than number of errors due to the effect of Persian language among the bilinguals. However, in the category of genitive by *for* the number of errors due to Persian language was greater though the difference was not significant.

Table 4.1: Type and number of errors by monolinguals and bilinguals due to the effect of language

Categories	Number of errors by monolinguals	Number of errors by bilinguals	
		Affected By Persian	Affected by Turkish
Possessive pronouns	132	78	95
Possessive adjectives	54	79	125
Possessive S	153	154	152
Genitive by <i>for</i>	28	40	37
Genitive by <i>of</i>	3	5	38
Genitive by <i>from</i>	9	5	-
Totals	379	361	447

4.1. Possessive Pronoun errors

The errors in the possessive pronoun questions were seen in both monolinguals and bilinguals. Persian speakers or monolinguals committed 132 errors. Bilinguals who spoke Turkish as their first language and Persian as the second one committed 78 errors due to the Persian language effect and 95 errors due to the Turkish language effect. Totally, bilinguals committed 173 errors in possessive pronouns, which is more than those of monolinguals. Chi-square was run on errors committed by monolinguals and bilinguals either affected by Persian or Turkish language.

Table 4.2: Chi- square tests for errors in possessive pronoun category affected by Persian language between monolinguals and bilinguals

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi- square	19.534	6	.003
N of valid cases	120		

As seen in the table 4.2, significance level is 0.003 which is lower than the confidence level of 0.05 showing that there is a statistically significant difference between monolinguals and bilinguals in terms of the effect of Persian language on *possessive pronoun* errors. Figure 4.1 shows the comparative frequency count of errors in *possessive pronouns* affected by Persian language between monolinguals and bilinguals.

Figure 4.1: Comparative frequency count of errors in *possessive pronouns* affected by Persian language between monolinguals and bilinguals

Table 4.3: Chi- square tests for errors in possessive pronoun category affected by first language between monolinguals and bilinguals

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	10.957	6	.090
N of Valid Cases	120		

As seen in the table 4.3, significance level is 0.09 which is higher than the confidence level of 0.05 showing that there is no statistically significant difference between monolinguals and bilinguals in terms of the effect of first language on *possessive pronoun* errors. This means that most of the errors committed by monolinguals and bilinguals were affected by their mother tongue. In other words, it can be cautiously concluded that negative transfer occurs in any language and mainly because of the effect of first language. Figure 4.2 shows the comparative frequency count of errors in *possessive pronouns* due to the effect of first language between monolinguals and bilinguals.

Figure 4.2: Comparative frequency count of errors in *possessive pronouns* due to the effect of first language between monolinguals and bilinguals

4.2. Possessive Adjective Errors

The errors in the *possessive adjective* questions were seen in both monolinguals and bilinguals. Persian speakers or monolinguals committed 54 errors. Bilinguals who spoke Turkish as their first language and Persian as second language committed 79 errors due to Persian language effect and 125 errors due to Turkish language effect. Totally, bilinguals committed 204 errors in possessive adjectives, which is more than those of monolinguals. The interesting point is that Turkish language as the first language has contributed more to the number of errors in this category compared with the effect of Persian language. Chi-square was run on errors committed by monolinguals and bilinguals either affected by Persian or Turkish.

Table 4.4: Chi- square tests for errors in possessive adjective category affected by Persian language between monolinguals and bilinguals

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi- Square	5.572	5	0.35
N of Valid Cases	120		

As seen in the table 4.4, significance level is 0.35; it is higher than the confidence level of 0.05 showing that there is no statistically significant difference between monolinguals and bilinguals in terms of the effect of Persian language on *possessive adjectives* errors.

Figure 4.3 shows the comparative frequency count of errors in *possessive adjectives* due to the effect of Persian language between monolinguals and bilinguals.

Figure 4.3: Comparative frequency count of errors in *possessive adjectives* due to the effect of Persian language between monolinguals and bilinguals

Table 4.5: Chi- square tests for errors in possessive adjective category affected by first language between monolinguals and bilinguals

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	32.323	6	.000
N of Valid Cases	120		

As seen in the table 4.5, significance level is 0.00; it is lower than the confidence level of 0.05 showing that there is a statistically significant difference between monolinguals and bilinguals in terms of the effect of first language on *possessive adjectives* errors. Figure 4.4 shows the comparative frequency count of errors in *possessive adjectives* due to the effect of first language between monolinguals and bilinguals.

Figure 4.4: Comparative frequency count of errors in *possessive adjectives* due to the first language effect between monolinguals and bilinguals

4.3. Possessive S

The errors in the *possessive S* category were seen in both monolinguals and bilinguals. Persian speakers or monolinguals committed 153 errors. Bilinguals who spoke Turkish as their first language and Persian as second one committed 154 errors due to Persian language effect and 152 errors due to Turkish language effect. Totally, bilinguals committed 237 errors in *possessive s*, which is more than those of monolinguals. The interesting point is that both languages contributed equally to the number of errors in this category. As there is not much difference between the numbers only comparative frequency count chart was used. Figure 4.5 compares the frequency count between monolinguals and bilinguals in terms of the effect of Persian language and 4.6 compares the frequency count between monolinguals and bilinguals in terms of the effect of first language.

Figure 4.5: Comparative frequency count of errors in *possessive S* due to the Persian language effect between monolinguals and bilinguals

Figure 4.6: Comparative frequency count of errors in *possessive S* due to the effect of first language between monolinguals and bilinguals

It seems that this category of errors has nothing to do with either Persian or Turkish language. Although bilinguals totally committed more errors, it needs to further clarify what the reasons have been because regarding the source of errors, both monolinguals and bilinguals committed the same number of errors.

4.4. Genitive by *For*

The errors in the genitive by *for* category were seen in both monolinguals and bilinguals. Persian speakers or monolinguals committed 28 errors. Bilinguals who spoke Turkish as their first language and Persian as second one committed 40 errors due to the Persian language effect and 37 errors due to the Turkish language effect. Totally, bilinguals committed 77 errors in *genitive by for*, which is more than those of monolinguals. Bilinguals' number of errors in this category, due to the effect of Persian and Turkish language, was close to each other.

On the other hand, monolinguals committed fewer number of errors compared with those of bilinguals either because of the effect of Persian or Turkish language. Chi-square test was run on errors committed by monolinguals and bilinguals either affected by Persian or Turkish language. Figure 4.7 compares the frequency count of errors in this category between monolinguals and bilinguals in terms of the effect of Persian language and 4.8 compares the frequency count of errors between monolinguals and bilinguals in terms of the effect of first language.

Table 4.6: Chi- square tests for errors in genitive by *for* category affected by Persian language between monolinguals and bilinguals

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi- Square	2.810	4	.590
N of Valid Cases	120		

As seen in the table 4.6. Significance level is 0.59; it is higher than the confidence level of 0.05 showing that there is no statistically significant difference between monolinguals and bilinguals in terms of the effect of the Persian language on genitive by *for* errors. Figure 4.7 shows the comparative frequency count of errors in genitive by *for* due to the effect of Persian language between monolinguals and bilinguals.

Figure 4.7: The comparative frequency count of errors in genitive by *for* due to the effect of Persian language between monolinguals and bilinguals

Table 4.7: Chi- square tests for errors in genitive by *for* category affected by first language between monolinguals and bilinguals

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi- Square	6.866	4	.143
N of Valid Cases	120		

As seen in the table 4.7, significance level is 0.14; it is higher than the confidence level of 0.05 showing that there is no statistically significant difference between monolinguals and bilinguals in terms of the effect of first language on *genitive by for* errors. Figure 4.8 shows the comparative frequency count of errors in genitive by *for* due to the effect of the first language between monolinguals and bilinguals.

Figure 4.8: The comparative frequency count of errors in genitive by *for* due to the effect of first language between monolinguals and bilinguals

4.5. Genitive by *of*

The errors in the Genitive by *of* category were seen in both monolinguals and bilinguals. Persian speakers or monolinguals committed 3 errors. Bilinguals who spoke Turkish as their first language and Persian as second one committed 5 errors due to the Persian language effect and 38 errors due to the Turkish language effect. Totally, bilinguals committed 43 errors in genitive by *of* category, which is more than those of monolinguals. In this category of errors, the effect of Persian language was seen little both on monolinguals and bilinguals. In other words, there were few errors committed by both monolinguals and bilinguals due to the effect of the Persian language. On the other hand, the errors due to the negative effect of the Turkish language were clearly evident. Out of 43 errors committed by bilinguals, only three of them were related to the effect of Persian language. Chi-square was run on errors committed by monolinguals and bilinguals either affected by Persian or Turkish language. Figure 4.9 compares the frequency count of errors in this category between monolinguals and bilinguals in terms of the effect of the Persian language and Figure 4.10 compares the frequency count of errors in genitive by *of* category between monolinguals and bilinguals in terms of the effect of their first language.

Table 4.8: Chi-square tests for errors in genitive by *of* category affected by Persian language between monolinguals and bilinguals

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.536	1	.464		
Fisher's Exact Test				.717	.359
N of Valid Cases	120				

Due to the limited number of items, Fisher's exact test was also run which showed a significant level of 0.717. This means that there was no significant difference between monolinguals and bilinguals in terms of the number of errors affected by the Persian language in *genitive by of* category. In other words, Persian language has not affected both monolinguals and bilinguals in terms of committing errors in this category to a great extent. Figure 4.9 shows the comparative frequency count of errors in *genitive by of* category due to the effect of Persian language between monolinguals and bilinguals.

Figure 4.9: The comparative frequency count of errors in *genitive by of* category due to the effect of Persian language between monolinguals and bilinguals

Table 4.9: Chi-Square Tests for errors in *genitive by of* category affected by first language between monolinguals and bilinguals

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	30.591	2	.000
N of Valid Cases	120		

Table 4.9 shows that significance level is 0.00; it is lower than the confidence level of 0.05 showing that there is a statistically significant difference between monolinguals and bilinguals in terms of the effect of first language on *genitive by of* errors. It can be concluded that the Turkish language has contributed to the number of errors in *genitive by of* category significantly more than the Persian language has done.

Figure 4.10: The comparative frequency count of errors in *genitive by of* category due to the effect of first language between monolinguals and bilinguals

4.6. Genitive by from

The errors in the *genitive by from* category were seen in both monolinguals and bilinguals. The Persian speakers or monolinguals committed 9 errors. Bilinguals who spoke Turkish as their first language and Persian as second one committed 5 errors due to the Persian language effect and no errors due to the Turkish language effect. Totally, monolinguals committed more errors in *genitive by from* category than bilinguals. In this category of errors, the effect of the Turkish language was not observed by bilinguals. Bilinguals totally committed 5 errors in this category and all of these errors were related to the Persian language. In other words, Persian language was the source of errors in the category of *genitive by from*. Therefore, the Persian language contributed more to the number of errors. Chi-square test was run on errors committed by monolinguals and bilinguals affected by the Persian language. Figure 4.11 compares the frequency count of errors in this category between monolinguals and bilinguals in terms of the effect of Persian language.

Table 4.10: Chi-Square Tests for errors in Genitive by *from* category affected by Persian language between monolinguals and bilinguals

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.294	1	.255		
Fisher's Exact Test				.394	.197
N of Valid Cases	120				

Due to the limited number of items Fisher's Exact Test was also run. Table 4.10 shows that both significant levels of Chi-Square (0.25) and Fisher's Exact Test (0.39) were higher than confidence interval of 0.05 which means that there was no significant difference between monolinguals and bilinguals in terms of number of errors in the category of genitive by *from* due to the effect of Persian language. Figure 4.11 shows the comparative frequency count of errors in genitive by *from* category between monolinguals and bilinguals due to the effect of Persian language.

Figure 4.11: The comparative frequency count of errors in genitive by *from* category between monolinguals and bilinguals due to the effect of Persian language

5. Discussion and Conclusion

In this study, the effect of the Persian language for monolinguals and the effect of both Persian and Turkish languages for bilinguals on the errors committed by monolinguals and bilinguals in six categories of genitive cases in English were investigated. The number, type, and sources of errors were identified. Regarding the effect of the mother tongue on negative transfer, the results of this study is in line with Jafarpour and Koosha (2006), Khodabande (2007), Ahmadvand (2008), Nayernia (2011), Basaty and Raghidoost (1392), Bayat (2012), Hedeshi (2012), Sattari (2012).

Regarding the sources of their errors, negative transfer could be attributed to both Persian and Turkish languages among the bilinguals and Persian language among the monolinguals. In the possessive pronoun category, the monolinguals committed 132 errors due to the effect of their first language, while bilinguals committed 95 errors. The statistical analyses also showed significant differences between them. However, looking more closely, one can find that bilinguals committed another 78 errors due to the effect of their second language (Persian). Therefore, it can be concluded that as long as interlingual effect is concerned, bilinguals commit the errors based on negative transfer from both first and second language.

In the possessive adjective category, monolinguals committed 54 errors and bilinguals committed 125 errors due to the effect of first language. It is implied that Turkish language has contributed more to the number errors committed by its speakers. Another proof for this is that in this category, bilinguals committed 79 errors due the effect of the second language (Persian) which was much fewer than those errors due to the effect of the first language (Turkish).

Considering that both English and Turkish require possessive adjectives before a noun, which is in contrast with Persian structure, it is very surprising that the Turkish participants committed more errors due to the effect of the Turkish language. One possible explanation can be the existence of a second language (Persian) in the mind of bilinguals, which has made leaning possessive adjectives complicated for them.

Another explanation can be the similarities between the Turkish and English languages, and not the differences. Bayat (2012) analyzed the effect of the Persian language as a native language on the learning of the possessive adjectives and pronouns of English by Iranian EFL learners, based on contrastive analysis and error analysis. She compared Persian possessive genitive case with English possessive adjectives and pronouns to finding out the source of their errors. In the study both similarities and differences of forms, meanings and usages of possessives in Persian and English languages were contrasted. The researcher stated that her study's results

showed that the errors of Persian speakers were just related to similarities not differences. Other explanations which can tentatively put forward are the effects of teacher's strategies, materials, teaching methodologies and many other contextual factors.

In the possessive *S* category, the effect of the first language on this kind of errors has been the same for both monolinguals and bilinguals. Bilinguals committed 154 and monolinguals committed 152 errors due to the effect of first language. However, bilinguals committed another 154 errors in this category which was due to the effect of second language (Persian). Again, it seems that the presence of a second language has complicated the learning of this category of genitive case for bilinguals.

In the genitive by *for* category, the trace of both first and second languages could be detected in errors committed by monolinguals and bilinguals. Bilinguals committed fairly equal number of errors due to the effect of their first and second languages and totally committed more errors compared with monolinguals. It can be hypothesized that again existence of a second language has made learning of this category of errors difficult for bilinguals.

Similar to possessive adjective category, the number of errors in genitive by *of* category due to the effect of the Persian language was much fewer than those due to the effect of the Turkish one among bilinguals and monolinguals. It is clearly evident that the Turkish speaker has had difficulty in the usage of this category of genitive case. In English and Persian for the genitive by *of* category, the added nouns come before the agent, while in Turkish, it is vice versa. It can be concluded that the Turkish grammatical structure has interfered with learning English structure regarding this category of genitives.

With respect to genitive by *from* category, the effect of the Persian on the errors in this category was observed while no cases of this type of error was observed due to the effect of the Turkish language. The interesting point is that the Persian language structure is more similar to the English one, but all observed errors for both monolinguals and bilinguals were due to the effect of the Persian language. As stated earlier, the reason could be due to the similarities between Persian and English rather than the differences.

6. Pedagogical Implications

This study confirmed the presence of the negative transfer from mother tongue as well the second language and therefore, it informs the language teachers to be aware of such a phenomena and do their best in applying appropriate teaching strategies to lower the

effect of the negative transfer. The fact that totally bilinguals committed more errors than monolinguals makes learning foreign language like English much more difficult for the Iranian bilinguals. Therefore, it requires special attention on the part of language educators, language teachers and material developers to fill possible educational gaps in reducing the difficulties bilinguals encounter.

As literature has shown us, the errors could be due to several factors among which the linguistic difference between the first and target languages is one of them. Therefore, a better planned teaching curriculum seems essential for bilingual language learners. As the study showed, monolinguals also suffer from the negative transfer of the mother tongue which warns the teachers, educators and material developers not to forget this group of learners as well. Evidence-based research for developing course materials is another area which needs particular attention. Those target structures which are more problematic due to the negative linguistic transfer need to be well developed and planned in the course materials.

7. Suggestions for Further Research

In this research, the researcher only used a test to identify the kind and source of errors committed by monolinguals and bilinguals in the usage of English genitive cases. The fact that such errors could be due to a variety of sources calls the researchers to detect the sources of errors in more qualitative methods such as think-aloud technique to get richer picture of the source of genitive case errors. Obviously, further research is also required to cover other aspects of English grammar which are affected languages such Persian and Turkish.

Moreover, it is also worth to mention that intralanguage and overgeneralization as other sources of errors need to be investigated along the interlanguage. In this way, we can get a more complete picture of sources of grammatical errors.

Finally, investigating the effect of both first and second languages on causing positive linguistic transfer is another area of research for future research. But as we encountered in our study, similarities did not prevent learners from committing errors in possessive adjective category for Turkish speakers and in genitive by *from* category for Persian speakers. More research is recommended into investigating the role of similarities in causing positive transfer.

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18. منابع فارسی
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